

Luminous flux through the vertical circle with medium

Harald Schröer

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We view a point source Q with vertical circle of radius R with distance r to Q and without medium as in the figure.

$$x \in [0, R] \quad r > 0$$

I = luminous intensity of Q

We want to calculate the luminous flux. $x \in [0, R]$ is the integration variable.

$$E(x) = \frac{I}{r^2 + x^2}$$

is the illumination at x .

$$\cos \beta(x) = \frac{r}{\sqrt{r^2 + x^2}}$$

$\beta(x)$ is the angle of inclination at x .

The luminous flux Φ through the circle can be written:

$$\Phi = \int_0^R 2\pi x \cdot E(x) \cdot \cos \beta(x) dx \quad (1)$$

$$= 2\pi I \cdot r \cdot \int_0^R \frac{x}{(r^2 + x^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} dx \quad (2)$$

substitution: $r^2 + x^2 = t$

$$x = \sqrt{t - r^2} \quad \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{t - r^2}}$$

$$t(R) = r^2 + R^2 \quad t(0) = r^2$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^R \frac{x}{(r^2 + x^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} dx &= \int_{r^2}^{r^2+R^2} \frac{dt}{2t^{\frac{3}{2}}} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{-2}{\sqrt{t}} \right]_{r^2}^{r^2+R^2} \\ &= \frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{r^2 + R^2}} \end{aligned}$$

It follows:

$$\Phi = 2\pi I r \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{r^2 + R^2}} \right) = 2\pi I \left(1 - \frac{r}{\sqrt{r^2 + R^2}} \right) \quad (3)$$

We look at the same situation with a medium (for example pure air). The medium is in the whole room. We assume that the absorption coefficient m is spatial and temporal constant. Then we add only the factor of absorption in equation (2).

$$\Phi = 2\pi I r \cdot \int_0^R e^{-m\sqrt{r^2+x^2}} \cdot \frac{x}{(r^2 + x^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} dx \quad (4)$$

$r > 0$

We show the dependence of luminous flux through the absorption with the following table. With the values $r=8\text{m}$, $R=4\text{m}$ and $I=30$ Candela we yield:

m[metre ⁻¹]	Φ [lumen]
0	19,90
0.0001	19.88
0.0002	19.87
0.0003	19.85
0.0004	19.83
0.0005	19.82
0.0006	19.80
0.0007	19.78
0.0008	19.77
0.0009	19.75
0.001	19.73
0.005	19.08
0.01	18.29
0.05	13.04
0.1	8.547
0.5	0.2931
0.6	0.1263
0.7	0.05450
0.8	0.02353
0.9	0.01017
1	0.004395
1.1	0.001901
1.2	0.0008232
1.3	0.0003566
1.4	0.0001546
1.5	0.00006706
1.6	0.00002911
1.7	0.00001264
1.8	0.000005496
1.9	0.000002390
2	0.000001040
2.1	0.0000004529
2.2	0.0000001973
2.3	0.00000008603
2.4	0.00000003753

We use Simpson's rule with 50 steps to calculate the integral.

References

- [1] Harald Schröer, "Luminous Flux and Illumination", Wissenschaft und Technik Verlag, Berlin, 2001